

(commercial grade, 96%) for 30 min increased germination to more than 90%. Seeds must be washed very quickly after treatment so as not to subject them to temperatures of more than 45 °C. Slow washing resulted in temperatures of about 110 °C that damaged seeds and resulted in very poor germination. Diluting commercial grade H₂SO₄ tenfold was not effective. □

Flowering, seed production, and germination of *Sesbania speciosa* used as green manure for lowland rice in Sri Lanka

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We evaluated the flowering, seed production, and germination of *S. speciosa* for use in a green manuring system for lowland rice in Sri Lanka.

The study was conducted in the ARS lowland experimental site at Maha Illuppallama, in the dry zone, Sri Lanka. Soil is Tropaqualf with pH of about 7.3, 4.4% organic matter, 0.095% total N, and 94 µg available P/g soil. We conducted a

year-round *S. speciosa* planting trial from Nov 1990 to Oct 1991.

During the first week of each month, we seeded a 5- × 4-m plot with *S. speciosa* at 0.05- × 0.5-m row spacing. Plots were irrigated once every 3 d and kept weed-free. We recorded dates of 50% flowering in the plots (a visual observation), podding, and seed setting.

Because seed germination can be as low as 30%, we applied two promising seed treatments—concentrated sulfuric acid for 40 min and 80°C water for 45 s—to improve germination in wet-sand cultures.

Monthly seeding of *S. speciosa* resulted in irregular flowering (see figure) and seed production. Seeding between Jan and Mar produced 5.6–8.5 g seed/plant; Apr–Aug, 12.1–15.5 g seed/plant; and Sep to Dec, 4.7, 4.4, 2.0, and 0.9 g seed/plant, respectively.

Seeding *S. speciosa* between May and Oct causes it to flower during Nov–Dec (see figure) and to pod and set seed in Jan–Feb. This schedule is the most efficient for

The effect of seed treatment on germination of *S. speciosa*.

Seed treatment	Germination ^a (%)
Acid	61 ± 5a
Hot water	35 ± 5 b
Control	20 ± 4 c

^a Germination (%) ± SE. Values followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level according to *x*²-test.

Effect of monthly daylength on flowering of *S. speciosa*. Circle that crosses the shaded sectors indicates 12 h photoperiod.

seed production because it concentrates seed setting into a period as short as 2 mo. Because *S. speciosa* is photoperiod sensitive, this seed production program is useful for tropical countries with similar monthly daylengths.

The acid treatment enhanced germination of *S. speciosa* significantly compared with the hot water treatment, which was significantly better than the control (see table). □

Ammonia excretion by *Anabaena azollae* immobilized in alginate and its effect on the growth of rice seedlings

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Azolla is a water fern that fixes atmospheric N in association with an algal symbiont. *A. azollae* can contribute 40–60 kg N/ha of a rice crop under low-cost rice production management.

We investigated the effect of immobilizing two strains of algal

1. Algal symbiont AS-K₄ immobilized in calcium alginate.

symbionts, *A. azollae* (AS-K₄) and (AS-S₁), and two free-living blue-green algae, *Anabaena* sp. (FL) and *Nostoc* sp. (FL), in calcium alginate on ammonia excretion and its influence on the growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

These N₂-fixing algal cultures were grown in IRRI N-free liquid medium for 2 wk in a growth room at 26 ± 1°C with 2000-3000 lux light intensity.

Suspensions were prepared from these cultures and mixed with an equal volume of calcium alginate aqueous solution (2.4%). The N content before immobilization in alginate was 2.96% for AS-K₄, 2.91% for AS-S₁, 3.14% for *Anabaena* sp., and 3.64% for *Nostoc* sp. Using a 10-ml pipette, the mixture of algal suspension in calcium alginate was added drop by drop to a solution containing 50 mM calcium chloride, resulting in the formation of round beads (Fig. 1). The algal beads were washed thoroughly, set on IRRI N-free medium, and incubated under the same growth room condition as the culture. Using Nessler's reagent method, we then measured ammonia excretion from the filtrate of the medium in which the algal beads had been maintained for 2 wk.

Nostoc sp., *A. azollae* (AS-K₄), *A. azollae* (AS-S₁), and *Anabaena* excreted 52.57, 34.28, 27.40, and 19.14 µg ammonia/m per 100 ml medium, respectively.

Forty IR64 rice seedlings that had been raised in sterile sand culture were maintained in a plastic cup. They were inoculated with 80 immobilized alginate algal beads (about 4,500 algal cells/algal bead). Sterile water was added and kept at a depth of 2.5 cm for 5 wk under controlled conditions. The seedlings were then carefully pulled out. Root, shoot growth, fresh biomass, and N

2. Effect of alginate-immobilized algal symbionts of azolla and free-living blue-green algae on growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

content were all significantly increased when plants were inoculated with alginate-immobilized algal beads. Inoculation with immobilized algal beads significantly increased the N content in IR64 rice seedlings over the control. N content ranged from .528% (*A. azollae* [AS-S₁]) to .588% (*Nostoc* [FL]) in the immobilized algal inoculated plants, and was .392% in the

control. Algal beads immobilized with *Nostoc* sp. produced the best seedling growth (Fig. 2).

The results showed that the immobilized algal symbionts of Azolla and free-living blue-green algae can continuously excrete ammonia that can be absorbed by rice seedlings and used in their growth. The cost of alginate beads at 5 kg/ha is \$7.5. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Antagonistic Soil bacteria for biological control of rice sheath blight (ShB) disease

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We explored the possibility of using antagonistic soil bacteria for biological control of ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn. We isolated bacteria from samples collected from areas covering four administrative divisions in Bangladesh. We tested 523 bacteria by placing two organisms in the plate

medium (dual culture method); 19.3% were antagonistic to varying degrees toward *R. solani* in vitro. Among these, 15% were fluorescent and 85% were nonfluorescent types.

Six bacteria were further tested for antagonism by dual culture and sclerotia dipping methods (Table 1). Isolate IS-